

Collaborative Development of Subject Teacher Deliberation and Professional Competence for the Improvement Quality of History Teachers

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ABSTRACT. This research aims to evaluate the collaborative development of subject teacher deliberation and professional competence for the improvement quality of history teachers. The subjects of the study were 30 history teachers. The questionnaire, observation, interview, and documents are a collection of data

from a sample of 10 male teachers and 20 female teachers from 16 public high schools in Banda Aceh City, Indonesia. The data from the questionnaire was analyzed quantitatively. The results of the research show that the level of tendency for subject teacher deliberation variables (X1), professional competence (X2), and quality of history teachers (Y) is in the sufficient category. The reliability test results obtained for subject teachers' deliberation variables and professional competency variables were 0.753, and the history teacher quality variable was 0.835, categorized as high. The correlational test results show a positive relationship between professional competence and the quality of history teachers. The achievement of each R square value is X1 of 0.321, or 32.1%, and X2 is 0.414, or 41.4%, suggesting that subject teachers' deliberation variables (X1) and professional competence (X2) have a significant relationship to the quality of history teachers. The reliability test results obtained for the subject teachers' deliberation and professional competency variables were 0.753, and the history teacher quality variable was 0.835, with a high category. There is a significant relationship between subject-teacher meetings and the quality of history teachers in Banda Aceh City Public High Schools. This means that, although there is still a lack of subject-teacher meetings attended by teachers, this results in low teacher professional competence; conversely, teachers' inadequate professional competence is directly caused by a lack of participation in subject-teacher meetings.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid social changes as a result of advancements in science and technology bring both positive and negative consequences for life. Until now, the role of educational institutions remains a pillar of hope that can bring enlightenment to a society undergoing change. Developed-nation students performed better than average on the 2022 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). Singapore and Estonia, for instance. Since the 1990s, several nations have implemented technology-based educational changes that have raised the standard of education. In the meanwhile, industrialized and developing nations differ greatly in how they are putting technology-based educational changes into practice. Technology-based education reforms in developed countries prioritize quality, efficiency, as well as equity and inclusion. In terms of equity and inclusion, disadvantaged groups of students and educators are given access to devices and resources. The country also provides a national digital learning platform. To improve the quality of learning, teachers in developed countries are given digital competency training, students are provided with personalized learning, learning environments are designed to engage interest, and digital competency achievements are set in the national curriculum.

To be efficient, educational institutions share knowledge. Advertisement Education Reform in Developing Countries According to studies, developing countries like Indonesia and India are on the right track to address pressing issues in their regions in the field of education. Teachers in Indonesia themselves face challenges: Limited resources Large class sizes Diverse culture Opportunities and access to training and professional development are limited. Low salary Hampered by logistics As a result, teachers struggle to pay attention to each student, manage diverse classrooms, keep up with updates in teaching methodologies, and reach remote areas. Indonesia also faces connectivity challenges like in India and Vietnam. Vietnam This ASEAN country is targeting the expansion of connectivity earlier than Indonesia and India, namely by 2025. Vietnam has allocated 3 trillion Vietnamese dong (IDR 1.92 trillion) to provide fiber optic cable internet services to all households before 2025, followed by efforts to enhance the national online learning program. This step is taken by the Vietnamese Government to reduce the household gap between rural and urban areas. As of 2021, 8 million local households do not have access to fiber optic cable internet services. India According to UNICEF data, 91 percent of school-age children in India do not have internet access at home, far above Vietnam (38 percent). Addressing the larger connectivity issue, the Indian government has chosen to focus on providing digital content at various access points through television, radio, community radio, and other mass media. This step was taken to reduce the access gap and the learning gap. Indonesia Like India, Indonesia also takes longer to address connectivity issues and the high cost of information and communication technology infrastructure. Indonesia itself has chosen to prioritize the use of technology to empower teachers and school principals. The development of the potential of teachers and school principals is expected to improve student educational outcomes. Indonesia uses a number of technological tools for this education quality improvement strategy. The Merdeka Mengajar platform, among others, responds to teachers' needs for equal access to learning opportunities and career development. On the same platform, teachers can share best practices from their schools with teachers in other regions online. The Education Report Card device contains data from the National Assessment and school evaluations to help school principals plan data-based improvements together with school residents and the community.

Quality in the world of education is a strategic agenda and has always been the most important task. Social change so rapidly as the impact of advances in science and technology has both positive and negative consequences for life. Until now, the role of educational institutions remains the focus of hope that can bring enlightenment to societies in change. In line with this, several policies outlined to improve the quality of education in general and improve the quality of history teachers in particular, include the following: First; conduct data collection, data validation, program development, and reporting system for educator professional development through a network with the Education Quality

Assurance Agency and the Aceh Education Office. Second; developing a model for the preparation and placement of educators in special areas through the formation of development teams and regional surveys. Third; formulate policies and develop an educator management system transparently and accountably through the establishment of a development team and a pilot educator management program. Fourth; enhancing staff capacity in program planning and evaluation through training and continuing education. (Wayan, L: 2011).

However, it cannot be denied that educational institutions are always lagging in the progress achieved by society. As a result, educational institutions need to make adjustments to all the developments in society. Referring to the Act of Aceh No. 11 of 2014 on the maintenance of education, Article 2 states that education in Aceh is based on: Islam, nationality, righteousness, truth, humanity, justice, utility, affordability, professionalism, equality, diversity, and non-discrimination. If a teacher is unable to communicate what is taught with pleasure, it will be difficult for the student to understand what is being taught. Therefore, to make it easier for students to study history, students should be able to understand the material by identifying the evidence of historical relics that still exist as a tool in the study of history. Without the resources of teachers who are superior in their fields, the quality of education in historical subjects will not improve. Education is not only a teaching that transfers science but also transforms science, values, and personality character formation from various aspects, both intellectual, spiritual, and emotional.

The dismissal of teachers of top-level high school subjects in the city of Banda Aceh was found to be less effective due to the lack of maximum and sustainable implementation as expected, namely, the return to the new normal, the motivation of the teacher to follow the teachers' dismissals of a subject is still low, the decision-making letter of the management is still temporarily, the directors of the dissemination of high-level teachers are not coordinated, and lack of support from the policymakers at the school level (head of school), district/city, province even to the central level. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out a high level of seriousness and commitment to re-optimize the role of teachers in high school subjects and a program that supports the managers of the teachers' assignments while improving the teacher's professionalism and the history teacher quality to become more compatible. The study conducted by Dheni Setiyawan (2015) shows that: (1) the quality of education services to high school students referring to the strategic plan of the Jombang education department in 2014-2018 as well as the Article 5 paragraph of Law No. 20 of 2003 on the National Education System (1) and article 11 paragraph (1) have not worked effectively; (2) factor that have a significant influence both from within (internal) and from outside (external) organizations of educational organizations. The factors that originate from within educational organizations are the existence of means and facilities, the motivation of teachers and students, the presence of competent teachers, and the innovation of education organizers. A factor outside

the educational organizations is the school's accessibility to a variety of resources, both resources and funds, that can support the operational teaching and learning activities.

The results of the study by Budiarta Plendes Suluh (2018) showed that the strategy of implementation of quality improvement policy in the State 1 Srandakan Primary School has been running following the objectives of its establishment, while the obstacles that appear in implementing quality enhancement policy are: low student understanding of the importance of education, insufficient number of educators, inadequate learning facilities, and the economic condition of the parents of students belong to the middle economy level down, also solutions to overcome obstacles in the implementation of quality improvement policies through an approach so that students want to continue their education to the next level, finding replacement teachers according to the subjects, procurement of facilities through the School Operational Assistance Fund, providing intelligent Indonesian programs for students who are not able.

Based on the observations and early observations of the writer to the school to develop the competence of the professional history teacher at the state high school of Banda Aceh there are many limitations experienced by the history teacher among others is not yet able to adapt to the change of curriculum, there has not been a significant awareness to enhance professionalism as a history teacher, there is still a lazy factor for the will to develop, there has never been a special training education for history teachers, and there is no sensitivity and responsiveness to various social changes.

In this case the researcher wants to know the research significance What is the description of the effectiveness of collaborative development of subject teacher quality and professional competence in improving the quality of history teachers in Banda Aceh City State High Schools?, and based background of this problem make the author feel motivated and challenged to study further this research with the title “Collaborative Development of Subject Teacher Deliberations and Professional Competence for the Improvement Quality of History Teachers.”

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of modern education has affirmed that the teacher as a profession as formulated by Abdul Majid (2012) as follows: Teaching as a profession refers to a role or occupation that calls for particular abilities and unique circumstances; It calls for a thorough understanding of teaching and education, as well as other related fields, and which must be fostered and developed over the course of a certain educational term. The professionalism of history teachers in teaching history will have an impact on students. The impact of professionalism in history learning such as students' mastery of knowledge, skills, and attitudes towards a subject. A history teacher must possess a thorough

understanding of the historical subject being taught to the student, as well as a command of its methodology, have a fundamental knowledge of education, have vital knowledge for the teacher, and have the right strategy in historical learning (Suroto, 2012). Teachers must have informed responsiveness so that students can cope with the problems that exist around them to be successful people in the future. Through the professionalism of future teachers' the country can be trusted.

In addition, the factors that influence the improvement of the quality of the history teacher at the State High School of Banda Aceh are the effectiveness of the teachers' teaching of historical subjects. The aim of forming this subject teachers' meeting is so that teachers can use and participate in this organization. Through teacher deliberations in this subject, teachers can exchange experiences, share between teachers, and improve the competence of professional teacher educators. Subject-teacher deliberations are a very efficient medium for increasing teacher competence and professionalism. Over time, subject-teacher deliberation has become a teacher upgrading system with a pattern of, by and for teachers. Based on the results of initial observations conducted by researchers in several schools, it shows that subject teacher deliberation activities in Banda Aceh City are routinely carried out once a week in each subject in state high schools, Meanwhile, the specific data collection for history teachers at Banda Aceh City state high schools is as follows: the employment status of history subject teachers is divided into three (3), namely (1) as civil servants, (2) as government employees with a work agreement, and (3) as an honorary employee, then after conducting a school survey, the total number of history teachers in Banda Aceh City state high schools was 31 history teachers.

Furthermore, the results of interviews with researchers, especially with history subject teachers, during subject teacher deliberation activities, show that the implementation of this subject teacher deliberation is supported by the policy of the Aceh Education Service which is implemented intensively at least 3 times a month. Meanwhile, the participants in the subject teacher deliberation rotate every week, so the participants alternate every week, but it also depends on each school to send their teachers to take part in the subject teacher deliberation activities. The program of activities carried out by the subject teachers' meeting should depend on the priority needs or problems faced by teachers when conducting learning, while the routine activities carried out by the subject teachers' meeting include discussing the preparation of teaching materials, making syllabi, and lesson implementation plans. and assessment. Seeing the current conditions, subject-teacher deliberation activities are only used as ceremonial events. Many teachers are full-time teaching, due to time constraints, costs, and lack of awareness in the organization, and school leaders have not been able to encourage history teachers in particular to direct these activities.

Furthermore, there are teaching errors that do not carry out procedures that should be implemented when carrying out the teaching and learning process. There are many views from people who say that subject-teacher deliberation

activities are only activities that do not contribute much to improving the quality of a teacher's teaching. The teacher's role in obtaining material and experience from these activities is not implemented or applied optimally in the process of teaching and learning.

In addition, considering the lack of effectiveness of these activities, efforts need to be made so that the deliberative role of history subject teachers can be carried out independently, proactively, and sustainably. Subject-teacher deliberations are a forum for activities to foster professional collaborative relationships between fellow teachers in the same subject. Subject-teacher deliberations are useful for teachers in improving their understanding of the curriculum, developing syllabi, learning implementation plans, assessment systems, designing teaching materials, and teaching practices that can be done with real teaching or peer teaching (Indrawati 2013). In connection with the relationship between the effectiveness of subject-teacher deliberations and teacher professional competence, subject-teacher deliberations as associations or teacher associations play a strategic role in improving and strengthening teacher competence through discussions, online webinars, workshops, and training. The main role is to facilitate teachers in the same field of study to exchange opinions and experiences. The most important thing for subject teacher deliberations to do is to strengthen the performance of subject teacher deliberations to strengthen the teachers' competence by empowering the subject teaching working group to meet the needs of teachers while at the same time, a teacher should also engage, and actively participate in subject teaching working group activities decided by members of the subject teaching working group (Santosa, 2018). This is important because it indicates that the teacher's mindset is more focused on summative implementation compared to formative.

On the other hand, there is still a large gap between the ability of the students of the national examination with the standards of national examinations. Because teachers are still weak in understanding curriculum concepts, analysis of teaching materials, and learning planning. Teachers of subjects have to help teachers solve problems, especially in the learning activities in the classroom. The teachers of historical subjects at Banda Aceh State High School discussed how to implement the curriculum-2013 and realize independent learning curricula such as the preparation and development of curriculums, the plan of learning programs, compiling educational materials based on information and communication technology, approaches, methods, techniques or learning strategies, evaluate learning, learning materials and media, learning resources, minimum proficiency criteria, remedial learning, questions about tests for different needs, analyze learning outcomes, compile programs and enrichment, and discuss various problems and find alternative learning solutions.

In addition to the differences between teachers of subjects that have a relationship to the quality of history teachers, professional competence is an indispensable factor in strengthening history teacher quality. Fathurohman and

Suryana (2012) define competence as the basic knowledge, skills, and values that are reflected in the habits of thinking and acting. Another meaning of competence is the specification of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes possessed by a person and their application in the workplace, in accordance with the standards of performance required by the field. According to the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary, "Competence is the ability to do something well." Rulam Ahmadi (2018) presented the basic understanding of competence is the relationship between the ability and performance of a person in creating optimal and maximum working conditions.

The professional competence of a teacher according to Uno (2012) is "a set of abilities that a teacher must have to perform his teaching duties well." Professional competence according to Anwar (2018) is "the mastery of the learning material broadly and in-depth that the teacher must possess, including knowledge of the subject's curriculum in school and the body of science that addresses the issue, as well as expertise in the methods and structure of its field. Below are key indicators for each of these sub-competences:

1. Learn the scientific material about the subject of study. This means that educators need to be aware of the curriculum's teaching materials; comprehend structure; scientific ideas and procedures that bolster and make sense of the content; recognize the connections between ideas in related fields and incorporate scientific ideas into the teaching and learning process.
2. Teachers must become proficient in research measures and critical analysis to expand their understanding of the subject matter. This is implied by mastering the structure and procedures of science.

Professional competence according to the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 14 of 2005 and Ministerial Regulation Number 16 of 2007 states that: professional competence is the ability to master learning materials broadly and deeply, which enables guiding students to meet the competency standards set in the national standards. Meriam (Anwar, 2018) suggests that the professional competencies that teachers must have are: (1) Understanding students' motivations; (2) Have students' learning needs; (3) Having a fairly mature understanding of theory and practice; (4) Understanding the needs of the community of education users; (5) Able to use various learning methods and techniques; (6) Having listening and communication skills (spoken and written language); (7) Knowing how to apply the material taught in real-life practice; (8) Having an open perspective to allow students to develop their interests; (9) Having the desire to continuously enrich his knowledge and continue his studies; and (10) Having the ability to evaluate a learning program.

Based on the results of the researcher's theoretical study on teachers' professional competence, the variables and indicators of teachers' professional competence as intended by the researcher can be formulated as follows:

1. Possessing the knowledge, framework, ideas, and scientific attitude that underpin the subjects being taught.
2. Understanding the fundamental skills and competency requirements of the subjects being taught.
3. Creating innovative teaching materials.
4. Develop professionalism continuously by engaging in reflective actions.
5. Developing oneself through the use of information and communication technology.

Education experts have different conclusions about how to create quality educational institutions. Jerome S. Arcaro (2007) defines quality as a structured process for improving output results. In the context of education, Edward Sallis (2015) explains in his book *Total Quality Management in Education* that quality is something related to passion and self-esteem. For every institution, quality is the main agenda, and improving quality is the most important task. Mutuality in education can be seen from the perspective of its relevance to societal needs, as well as whether graduates can continue to the next level or even secure a good job, and a person's ability to overcome life's problems. The quality of education can be viewed from the benefits of education for individuals, society, and the nation or state. Specifically, some view the quality of education in terms of the depth and breadth of knowledge that an individual aims to achieve through their education.

According to Engkoswara and Aan Komariah (2015), the indicators of a quality school are (1) good inputs; (2) high work enthusiasm; (3) high motivation to learn; (4) proportional use of costs, time, facilities, and effort; (5) trust from various parties; (6) quality graduates; and (7) outputs that are relevant to the needs of the community. Furthermore, according to the Directorate General of Primary and Secondary Education of the Ministry of Education and Culture in 2017, the measures of success in quality assurance by educational units consist of process, output, outcome, and impact indicators. The explanation of the four indicators is as follows: (1) The input indicator is the increased capability of educational units in carrying out the cycle of education quality assurance, as evidenced by modifications to the administration of educational units; the presence and application of policies referencing national education standards; the improved capacity to organize and carry out quality fulfillment plans that have been developed; and the increased ability to monitor and evaluate the mechanisms that have been carried out; (2) The output indicator is the realization of improved education quality in educational units, demonstrated by the increased competencies of educators in carrying out the learning process from planning to assessment, the development of extracurricular activities, the improvement of the management of facilities and finances, collaboration and involvement of all stakeholders; (3) Outcome indicators, namely the improvement of student

learning outcomes; results of competency tests and performance assessments of educators and educational staff; achievements of educational units and their members; the realization of a pleasant learning environment; the presence of awards and financial support from stakeholders, and (4) Impact indicators, namely the establishment of a quality culture through the implementation of continuous and sustainable quality assurance in educational units.

Engkoswara and Aan Komariah (2015) explains that the quality standards of education can be referenced from the national education standards that have established minimum criteria for the education system in Indonesia, including:

1. Graduate competency standards
2. Content standards
3. Standard Process
4. Standards for educators and educational personnel
5. Standard of facilities and infrastructure
6. Management standards
7. Financing standards
8. Educational assessment standards

Amelia (2014) outlines several indicators related to history learning, namely: (1) history learning has objectives, substance, and targets in normative aspects; (2) The values and meanings of history are directed towards the interests of educational goals rather than pure academic or scientific purposes; (3) The history learning application is pragmatic in nature, so the dimensions and substance are selected and adjusted to the goals, meanings, and educational values that are intended to be achieved, in accordance with educational objectives; (4) Normative history learning must be relevant to the formulation of national education goals; (5) History learning must include essential elements: instruction, intellectual training, and responsibility for the future of the nation; (6) History learning not only presents factual knowledge of collective experiences from the past, but it must also provide exercises in critical thinking to extract meaning and values from the historical events being studied.

Based on the explanations provided in the literature review and the framework of thought, this research formulates the hypothesis that subject teachers' deliberation and professional competence have an impact on the improvement of the quality of history teachers at State Senior High Schools in Banda Aceh City.

The statistical hypothesis can be formulated into two hypotheses: the null hypothesis (H_0) and the alternative hypothesis (H_A). The statistical hypotheses are as follows:

H_0 = The subject teacher meetings and professional competencies do not have a relationship with the improvement of the quality of history teachers at State High Schools in Banda Aceh City.

H_A = The teachers' forum for subject matter and professional competence has a relationship with the improvement of the quality of history teachers at State High Schools in Banda Aceh City.

The framework of this research regarding the relationship between subject teachers' deliberation and professional competence in improving the quality of history teachers at public high schools in Banda Aceh can be seen in the following figure 1:

Figure 1: Research Framework Diagram

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research uses quantitative data analysis techniques with a correlational method. The correlational method explains the relationship between variables. Correlational research must examine two variables that have continuous values. A correlational study can investigate the relationship between motivation and academic achievement, both continuous variables. (Syaukani, 2015). The population of this study consists of all history teachers from public high schools in the city of Banda Aceh, totaling 30 participants. The entire population in this study was used as a sample by employing the census method or saturated sampling. This method requires that all members of the population be included as respondents or samples. (Sugiono, 2010).

The instrument technique used in this research is a questionnaire. This questionnaire is used to obtain primary data directly from the research subjects who will be subjected to the conclusions of the study. Before the instrument is used for testing, it is necessary to conduct validity and reliability tests first. Validity and reliability tests are carried out to determine which items meet the criteria and which do not. If they do not meet the criteria, they are not included in

the instrument. The instrument trial was conducted with high school teachers in Banda Aceh City-Indonesia. The minimum requirement for an item to be considered a valid instrument is that the validity index must be ≥ 0.3 (Sugiyono, 2016). Therefore, all statements with a correlation level below 0.3 must be revised as they are deemed invalid. The data processing was conducted using SPSS software Version 25 and the Excel program as a supporting tool.

To test the validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was trialed with 30 respondents. The respondents are the History teachers from the State High School in Banda Aceh. The calculated r result is compared with the table r to analyze its validity results. It is known: $N=30$, $df=28$, significance 5%, then the table $r = 0.361$. An instrument is considered valid if the calculated r (r count) is equal to or greater than the table r (r table) at a significance level of 5%. Conversely, the instrument is deemed invalid if the calculated r is less than the table r .

The reliability testing of the instrument is conducted using Cronbach's Alpha formula because the data is in the form of interval data. The formula for Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient (Nurgiyantoro, 2012) is as follows.

$$r_{11} = \frac{k}{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum \sigma_i^2}{\sigma^2} \right)$$

After conducting a reliability test using Excel, the reliability coefficient can be obtained. The criteria for decision-making to determine its reliability is that if the r value (Cronbach's alpha) is greater than 0.60, then the instrument is considered reliable. Conversely, if the r value (Cronbach's alpha) is less than 0.60, then the instrument is deemed unreliable. Next, a normality test is conducted, which aims to determine whether the data to be tested is normally distributed or not. To test the normality of data using the Chi-Square Test (χ^2) (Riduwan, 2007) with the following formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{(fo - fe)^2}{fe}$$

Next, a linearity test is conducted to determine whether there is a significant linear relationship between the two variables. The linearity test in this study aims to see if there is a relationship between the variable of Teacher Subject Deliberation (X1) and the variable of History Teacher Quality (Y), and the relationship between the Professional Competence variable (X2) and the History Teacher Quality variable (Y). This test is usually used as a prerequisite in correlation or linear regression analysis. The basis of decision-making:

- a. If the probability value is > 0.05 , it is said that the relationship between variables X and Y is linear.
- b. If the probability value is < 0.05 , then it is said that the relationship between variables X and Y is non-linear. (Joko Widiyanto, 2015)

Testing for linearity aims to determine whether a variable has a significant linear relationship or not. Software testing in Excel using the test of linearity at a significance level of less than 0.05 is one of the assumptions of regression analysis, which is linearity. The linearity test is conducted to prove the linearity of the regression equation for variable Y by testing the hypothesis of the linearity of the regression equation. The method for finding the F test value uses the formula (Sudjana, 2015).

$$F_{hitung} = \frac{RJK_{TC}}{RJK_e}$$

Determining the measurement criteria, if the calculated F value is less than the table F value, then the distribution is linear. To find the F table value at a significance level of 95% or $\alpha = 5\%$, you can use the formula $F_{table} = F(1-\alpha)$ (df TC, df E) where df TC = k-2 (numerator degrees of freedom) and df E = n-k (denominator degrees of freedom). This involves comparing the calculated F value (F count) with the F table value.

Statistical hypothesis:

HO : $Y = \alpha + \beta x$

Ha : $Y \neq \alpha + \beta x$

The criteria for testing the linearity of regression are:

Reject Ho if F calculated > F table, then it is a non-linear regression.

Accept Ho if F calculated < F table, then it is a linear regression.

In this study, the researcher used Pearson Product Moment correlation (r). The correlation test is used to determine the strength of the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. In hypothesis testing, if the correlation coefficient is significant, then this coefficient can be used to calculate the coefficient of determination, which is a coefficient that can be used to measure the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Sugiyono (2019) explains that there are several levels of correlation relationships between variables based on the coefficient interval, namely in Table 1:

Table 1. Interval of Correlation Coefficients Between Variables

Interval Coefficient	Relationship Level
0.00-0,199	Very Low
0.20-0,399	Low
0.40-0,599	Currently
0.60-0,799	Strong
0.80-1,000	Very Strong

Source: (Sugiyono, 2019)

In determining the r table, researchers can use the sample size (n) and the significance level applied (5%). In this study, the researcher used an r table value of 0.361, which was obtained by determining the r table with a sample size of 30 and a significance level of 5% from the product moment r value table. (Sugiyono, 2019). Furthermore, if the correlation coefficient (calculated r) is proven to be

significant, then the correlation coefficient can be used to measure the coefficient of determination.

KOEFISIEN DETERMINASI (R²)

According to Sugiyono (2019), the definition of the coefficient of determination is the ability of variable X (independent variable) to influence variable Y (dependent variable). The larger the coefficient of determination, the better the ability of X to explain Y. The formula for the coefficient of determination is as follows:

$$Kd = R^2 \times 100\%$$

Description:

Kd = Coefficient of determination

R = Correlation Coefficient

The interpretation of the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable is as follows Table 2:

Table 2. Interpretation of the Results of the Determination Coefficient Analysis

Statement of Reality	Statement of Reality
> 4%	Very low influence
5% - 16%	A low but steady influence
17% - 49%	A significant influence
50% - 80%	The influence of height or strength
>80%	Very high influence

Source: Sugiyono, (2017)

The purpose of the determination coefficient test is to determine how much the independent variable can explain the dependent variable. The determination test can be seen through an R square, and an R square value is considered good if it is above 0.05 (Nurmilasari, 2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The description of the research data presented on these three variables is the subject teacher meeting (X1), professional competence (X2), and the quality of history teachers (Y).

Results

Based on the quantification results of the respondent's answers to the questionnaire distributed in 30 sets, following the predetermined sample size for the research among the high school history teachers in Banda Aceh. After obtaining the raw data, the researcher processes the data using the SPSS Version 25 Windows software. The statistical data units can be seen in the following Table 3.

Table 3. Unit Data Statistical Results

N	Valid	30	30	30
	Missing	0	0	0
Mean		111.70	83.73	50.13
Std. Error of Mean		1.942	1.997	1.016
Median		112.00	85.00	49.00
Mode		120 ^a	101	55
Std. Deviation		10.635	10.938	5.563
Variance		113.114	119.651	30.947
Range		46	36	22
Minimum		90	65	40
Maximum		136	101	62
Sum		3351	2512	1504

a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown

Source: Data processed using SPSS Version 25 by the researcher, September 2024.

Next, the frequency distribution and histogram of each research variable are presented. The frequency distribution of the scores for the subject teachers' deliberation variable can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Frequency Distribution of the Subject Teacher Deliberation Variable

Class	Class Interval	Class Rules	Absolute Frequency (fi)	Relative Frequency	Cumulative Frequency
1	90 – 98	89.5 - 98.5	2	6.67 %	6.67 %
2	99 – 107	98.5 - 107.5	8	26.67 %	33.34 %
3	108 – 116	107.5 - 116.5	9	30 %	63.34 %
4	117 – 125	116.5 - 125.5	10	33.33 %	96.67 %
5	126 – 134	125.5 - 134.5	-	-	-
6	135 – 143	134.5 - 143.5	1	3.33 %	100 %
Amount			30	100%	

The histogram display of the subject teachers' deliberation variable can be seen in the following Figure 2:

Based on the data in Tables 3 and 4, it is known that the highest score is 136, the lowest score is 90, the average is 113, and the standard deviation is 8. Thus, 10 people (33.33%) of the respondents scored above average, while 2 people (6.67%) scored below average. Suharsimi Arikunto (2006) explains that to identify the tendencies of each variable in this research, the ideal mean score (M_i) and the ideal standard deviation (SD_i) of each variable are used, following the normal curve. Based on the ideal mean score and ideal standard deviation, they are categorized into four groups with the following norms:

Table 5. Frequency Distribution of Variables and Score Categories of the Research Variables

Class	Class Interval	Frequency of Observation	Relative Frequency	Category
1	$> (M_i + 1.5 SD_i)$ up to the ideal maximum score	FO ₁	FR ₁	High
2	$> M_i$ s/d $(M_i + 1.5 SD_i)$	FO ₂	FR ₂	Sufficient
3	$> (M_i - 1.5 SD_i)$ s/d M_i	FO ₃	FR ₃	Lacking
4	Ideal minimum score up to $(M_i - 1.5 SD_i)$	FO ₄	FR ₄	Low

By following the criteria in the methodology section, the tendency of the subject teachers' deliberation variable (X1) can be seen in Table 6 as follows.

Table 6. Level of Tendency of Subject Teacher Deliberation Variables (X1)

Stretching	Frequency of Observation	Relative Frequency	Category
124.5 – 136	3	10 %	High
113 – 124.5	11	36.67 %	Sufficient
101.5 – 113	11	36.67 %	Lacking
90 – 101.5	5	16.66 %	Low
Amount	30	100%	

Based on Table 6, it was found that 36.67 percent of the research subjects, namely the subject teacher deliberations (X1) at public high schools in Banda Aceh, fall into sufficient categories. Therefore, it can be concluded that the subject teacher deliberations tend to be in the "sufficient" category overall.

Professional Competence (X2)

The frequency distribution of the professional competency variable scores can be seen in Table 7 below.

Table 7. Frequency Distribution of the professional competency Variable

Class	Class Interval	Class Rules	Absolute Frequency (fi)	Relative Frequency	Cumulative Frequency
1	65 – 71	64.5 - 71.5	5	17 %	17 %
2	72 – 78	71.5 - 78.5	5	17 %	34 %
3	79 – 85	78.5 - 85.5	5	16 %	50 %
4	86 – 92	85.5 - 92.5	9	30 %	80 %
5	93 – 99	92.5 - 99.5	3	10 %	90 %
6	100 – 106	99.5 - 106.5	3	10 %	100 %
Amount			30	100%	

The histogram display of the professional competency variable can be seen in Figure 3 below:

Based on the data in Tables 3 and 7, it is known that the highest score is 101, the lowest score is 65, the average is 83, and the standard deviation is 6. Thus, 9 people (30%) of the respondents have scores above the average, and 4 people (12%) of the respondents are below the average.

Table 8. Level of Tendency of Professional Competency Variables (X2)

Stretching	Frequency of Observation	Relative Frequency	Category
92 – 101	7	23.5 %	High
83 – 92	10	33 %	Sufficient
74 – 83	7	23.5 %	Lacking
65 – 74	6	20 %	Low
Amount	30	100%	

Based on Table 8, it was found that 33 percent of the research subjects, namely professional competence (X2) at public high schools in Banda Aceh, fall into the "Sufficient" category. Therefore, it can be concluded that professional competence tends to be in the "Sufficient" category overall.

Quality of History Teachers (Y)

The frequency distribution of the scores for the history teacher quality variable can be seen in Table 9 below.

Table 9. Frequency Distribution of the Quality Variable of History Teachers

Class	Class Interval	Class Rules	Absolute Frequency (fi)	Relative Frequency	Cumulative Frequency
1	37 – 40	36.5 - 40.5	3	10 %	10 %
2	41 – 44	40.5 – 44.5	6	20 %	30 %
3	45 – 48	44.5 - 48.5	7	23.33 %	53.33 %
4	49 – 52	48.5 - 52.5	8	26.67 %	80 %
5	53 – 56	52.5 - 56.5	6	20 %	100 %
6	57 - 60	56.5 - 60.5	0	0	0
	Amount		30	100%	

The histogram display of the quality of history teachers variable can be seen in the following Figure 4:

Based on the data in Tables 4 and 10, it is known that the highest score is 62, the lowest score is 40, the average is 46, and the standard deviation is 3. Thus, 11 people (36.67%) of the respondents scored above average, while 5 people (16.66%) scored below average.

Table 10. Level of Quality Tendency of History Teachers (Y)

Stretching	Frequency of Observation	Relative Frequency	Category
50.5 – 55	8	26.67 %	High
46 – 50.5	11	36.67 %	Sufficient
41.5 – 46	5	16.66 %	Lacking
37 – 41.5	6	20 %	Low
Amount	30	100%	

Based on Table 10, it was found that 36.67 percent of the research subjects, namely the quality of history teachers (Y) in public high schools in Banda Aceh, fall into the "Satisfactory" category. Therefore, it can be concluded that the quality of history teachers tends to be in the "Sufficient" category overall.

Testing Analysis Requirements

The collected data is organized systematically as the following appendix and analyzed to prove the formulated hypothesis. The requirements for data analysis using linear regression are that the population data must be normally distributed and the independent variable must be linear concerning the dependent variable.

Normality Test

If $\rho > 0.05$, then the obtained data is normally distributed, and if $\rho < 0.05$, then the obtained data is not normally distributed.

1. Normality Test of Subject Teacher Deliberation Variable (X1)

In the normality test of variable X1, the first step is to create a summary table for variable X1, followed by calculations using the steps and formulas as follows:

Table 11. Summary of Normality Test Results for Variable X1

No	Class Interval Limits	f _i	X _i	x _i ²	f _i .x _i	x _i -x _{bar}	(x _i -x _{bar}) ²	f _i .(x _i -x _{bar}) ²
1	90 – 98	2	94	8836	188	-18.3	334.89	669.78
2	99 – 107	8	103	10609	824	-9.3	86.49	691.92
3	108 – 116	9	112	12544	1008	-0.3	0,09	0.81
4	117 – 125	10	121	14641	1210	8.7	75.69	756.9
5	126 – 134	0	130	16900	0	17.7	313.29	0
6	135 – 143	1	139	19321	139	26.7	712.89	712.89
		n = 30	699	82851	3369			2832.3
Average (\bar{X}) = $(\sum f_i \cdot x_i) / (\sum f_i)$					= 112.3			
Standard Deviation = $\sqrt{\sum f_i (x_i - \bar{X})^2 / n}$					= 9.7165			

Next, to calculate Chi Square, it can be computed using the following formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{(f_o - f_e)^2}{f_e}$$

It is known:

$k = 6 - 3 = 3$, and $\alpha = 0.05$

Table values $\chi^2 = 7.815$

Thus, after carrying out the calculations, the Chi-Square value is 5.125672.

Significance of the Test: The calculated χ^2 value is compared with the table χ^2 value (Chi-Square).

- If the calculated χ^2 value is less than the table χ^2 value, then H_0 is accepted: H_a is rejected (normally distributed).
- If the calculated χ^2 value is greater than the table χ^2 value, then H_0 is rejected: H_a is accepted.

Thus, the conclusion is reached: The population of subject teachers' discussions is normally distributed.

2. Normality Test of Professional Competence Variable (X2)

In the normality test of the professional competence variable, the first step is to create a summary table of variable X2, followed by calculations using the steps and formulas as follows:

Table 12. Summary of Normality Test Results for Variable X2

No	Class Interval Limits	f _i	x _i	x _i ²	f _i .x _i	x _i -x̄	(x _i -x̄) ²	f _i .(x _i -x̄) ²
1	65 - 71	5	68	4624	340	-16.1	259.21	1296.05
2	72 - 78	5	75	5625	375	-9.1	82.81	414.05
3	79 - 85	5	82	6724	410	-2.1	4.41	22.05
4	86 - 92	9	89	7921	801	4.9	24.01	216.09
5	93 - 99	3	96	9216	288	11.9	141.61	424.83
6	100 - 106	3	103	10609	309	18.9	357.21	1071.63
		n = 30	513	44719	2523			3444.7
Average (X̄) = (∑f _i .x _i)/(∑f _i)					= 84.1			
Standard Deviation = √∑f _i (x _i - X̄) ² /n					= 10.715			

Next, to calculate Chi Square, it can be computed using the following formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{(f_o - f_e)^2}{f_e}$$

So after doing the calculations, the Chi-Square value is 5.0875.

Significance Test: The calculated X² value is compared with the table X² (Chi-Square).

- If the calculated X² value < X² table, then Ho is accepted: Ha is rejected (normally distributed).
- If the calculated X² value > X² table, then Ho is rejected: Ha is accepted
- So the conclusion is obtained: The population of professional competence is normally distributed.

3. History Teacher Quality Variable Normality Test (Y)

The first step taken is to create a summary table of variable Y, followed by calculations using the steps and formulas as follows:

Table 13. Summary of Normality Test Results for Variable Y

No	Class Interval Limits	f _i	x _i	x _i ²	f _i .x _i	x _i -x̄	(x _i -x̄) ²	f _i .(x _i -x̄) ²
1	37 - 40	3	38.5	1482.25	115.5	-9.07	82.20	246.61
2	41 - 44	6	42.5	1806.25	255	-5.07	25.67	154.03
3	45 - 48	7	46.5	2162.25	325.5	-1.07	1.14	7.96
4	49 - 52	8	50.5	2550.25	404	2.93	8.60	68.84
5	53 - 56	6	54.5	2970.25	327	6.93	48.07	288.43
6	57 - 60	0	58.5	3422.25	0	10.93	119.54	0
		n = 30	291	14393.5	1427			765.87
Average (X̄) = (∑f _i .x _i)/(∑f _i)					= 47.57			
Standard Deviation = √∑f _i (x _i - X̄) ² /n					= 5.05			

Next, to calculate Chi Square, it can be computed using the following formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{(f_o - f_e)^2}{f_e}$$

So after the calculation, the Chi-Square value obtained is 3.28.

Significance of the Test: The calculated X^2 value is compared with the table X^2 value (Chi-Square).

- If the calculated X^2 value is less than the table X^2 value, then H_0 is accepted: H_a is rejected (normally distributed).
- If the calculated X^2 value is greater than the table X^2 value, then H_0 is rejected: H_a is accepted.

Thus, the conclusion is obtained: The quality population of history teachers is normally distributed.

Based on the test results, shows that the calculated X^2 value $<$ X^2 table for all variables, so it can be stated that the research data meets the normal distribution.

Linearity Test

Linearity testing aims to determine whether the relationship between variable X and variable Y is linear or not. The linearity test in this research was carried out with the help of SPSS version 25.0 for Windows. The basis for decision-making in the linearity test is:

- If the significance value is $>$ 0.05, then the relationship between variables X and Y is linear.
- If the significance value is $<$ 0.05, then the relationship between variables X and Y is non-linear. (Gozhali, 2006)

The linearity test of the data in this study is presented in the table below:

- Test the linearity between variables X1 and Y.

Referring to the criteria if $\rho >$ 0.05, it can be concluded that the correlation is linear, and if $\rho <$ 0.05, it can be concluded that the correlation is non-linear.

Table 14. Results of the Linearity Test of Variable X2 against Y

ANOVA Table

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Quality of History Teachers* Subject Teacher Deliberation	Between (Combined)	543.867	20	27.193	.944	.569
	Linearity	257.689	1	257.689	8.943	.015
	Deviation from Linearity	286.178	19	15.062	.523	.888
	Within Groups	259.333	9	28.815		
Total		803.200	29			

Based on the summary results in Table 14, the significance of the deviation from linearity is $>$ 0.05, specifically 0.888 $>$ 0.05, thus it can be stated that the relationship between the subject teachers' deliberation (X1) and the quality of history teachers (Y) is linear. The analysis results show that the price of F tuna is suitable = 0.944; with a significance of 0.888 (sig $>$ 0.05). This means that it is linear regression. Furthermore, the results of the linearity test in the F test table indicate that the linearity test between subject teacher meetings and the quality of history teachers yielded a calculated F value of 0.944 and a table F value of 3.354 ($F_h <$ F_t), which shows that the relationship between subject teacher meetings and the quality of history teachers is linear.

2. Test the linearity between variables X2 and Y.

Referring to the criteria if $\rho > 0.05$, it can be concluded that the correlation is linear, and if $\rho < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the correlation is non-linear.

Table 15. Results of the Linearity Test of Variable X2 against Y

			Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Quality of History Teachers * Professional competence	Between Groups	(Combined)	654.200	22	29.736	1.397	.340
		Linearity	254.541	1	254.541	11.958	.011
		Deviation from Linearity	399.659	21	19.031	.894	.612
	Within Groups	149.000	7	21.286			
Total			803.200	29			

Based on the summary results in Table 15, the significance of deviation from linearity is > 0.05 , specifically $0.612 > 0.05$, thus it can be stated that the relationship between professional competence (X2) and the quality of history teachers (Y) is linear. The analysis results show that the price of F tuna is suitable at 1.397, with a significance of 0.612 (sig > 0.05). This means that it is a linear regression. Furthermore, the results of the linearity test in the F test table show that the linearity test between professional competence and the quality of history teachers yielded a calculated F value of 1.397 and a table F value of 3.354 ($F_h < F_t$), indicating that the relationship between professional competence and the quality of history teachers is linear.

Hypothesis Testing in Research

1) Uji Korelasional Correlational Test

Testing the correlation using the following criteria:

Hypothesis 1

H0: There is no relationship between subject teacher deliberation and the quality of history teachers.

H1: There is a relationship between subject teacher deliberation and the quality of history teachers.

Hypothesis 2

H0: There is no relationship between professional competence and the quality of history teachers.

H1: There is a relationship between professional competence and the quality of history teachers.

		Subject teacher deliberation	Professional competence	Quality of history teachers
Subject teacher deliberation	Pearson Correlation	1	.542**	.566**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002	.001
	N	30	30	30
Professional competence	Pearson Correlation	.542**	1	.563**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002		.001
	N	30	30	30
Quality of history teachers	Pearson Correlation	.566**	.563**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.001	
	N	30	30	30

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The significance value (2-tailed) between the subject teachers' deliberation and the quality of history teachers is less than 0.05 ($0.001 < 0.05$), indicating that there is a correlation between the tested variables. Similarly, the significance value of professional competence in relation to the quality of history teachers is 0.001, which is less than 0.05. This means there is a relationship between subject teachers' deliberation and professional competence concerning the quality of history teachers. The conclusion can also be drawn from the calculated r value. For example, based on the calculated r value between the subject teachers' deliberation and the quality of history teachers, which is 0.566, and the table r value (30:0.05) which is 0.361. Since the calculated r is greater than the table r ($0.566 > 0.361$), there is a positive relationship between the subject teachers' deliberation and the quality of history teachers. Similarly, the correlation between professional competence and the quality of history teachers is 0.563, and the table value (30:0.05) is 0.361. Because the calculated r is greater than the table r ($0.563 > 0.361$), there is a positive relationship between professional competence and the quality of History teachers. This means that the greater the activities of the MGMP and professional competencies, the higher the quality of history teachers will be. So, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

1) Test the Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

According to Ghozali (2016), the coefficient of determination essentially measures the extent to which independent variables explain the variation in the dependent variable. The value of the coefficient of determination ranges between zero and one. A small R^2 value means that the ability of the independent variables to explain the variation in the dependent variable is minimal. Values close to one for independent variables provide almost all the information needed to predict the variation of the dependent variable. The purpose of the coefficient of determination test is to determine how much the independent variables can explain the dependent variable. The determination test can be assessed through R square, which is considered good if it is above 0.05. (Nurmilasari, 2019).

Table 16. SPSS Output Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.566 ^a	.321	.297	4.414

a. Predictors: (Constant), Subject teacher deliberation

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.643 ^a	.414	.370	4.177

a. Predictors: (Constant), Professional competence, Subject teacher deliberation

It is known that the R square value obtained is 0.321 or 32.1%, which indicates that the variable of teacher subject deliberation (X_1) has a significant relationship

(influence) on the quality of history teachers by 32.1%. It is known that the R square value obtained is 0.414 or 41.4%, which indicates that the variable of professional competence (X2) has a significant relationship (influence) on the quality of history teachers amounting to 41.4%.

DISCUSSION

The Collaborative Development Between Subject Teacher Meetings and Professional Competence on the Quality of History Teachers

Based on field data regarding the relationship between subject teacher deliberation and professional competence in improving the quality of history teachers at public high schools in Banda Aceh, sourced from statistical data processed using SPSS Version 25, following the summary criteria in the methodology section, it can be concluded that the tendency level of the variables of teacher subject deliberation (X1), professional competence (X2), and the quality of history teachers (Y) falls into the sufficient category.

From the results of the reliability test, the variable of the quality of subject teachers and professional competence obtained a score of 0.753, while the variable of the quality of history teachers scored 0.835. The decision-making criteria for determining reliability state that if the r value (Cronbach's alpha) is greater than 0.60, then the instrument is considered reliable, consequently, it may be said that the three previously listed factors fall under the high category.

Furthermore, based on the results of the data analysis in the normality test, the researcher used the Chi-Square Test (χ^2) sourced from Riduwan's reference. (2013), so, to calculate the Chi-Square that refers to the significance criteria of the test, That is, if the calculated X^2 value is less than the table X^2 value, then H_0 is accepted: H_a is rejected (normally distributed). Using the SPSS software tool Version 25 and Excel program according to the criteria that if $p > 0.05$; then the data obtained is normally distributed and if $p < 0.05$ then the data obtained is not normally distributed. So it can be stated that the research data on the variables of subject teacher quality, professional competence, and history teacher quality have been fulfilled from a normally distributed population.

Based on the linearity test with calculations referring to the criteria that if $p > 0.05$ then it can be concluded that the correlation is linear, and if $p < 0.05$ then it can be concluded that the correlation is non-linear (Joko Widiyanto, 2015: 53). The analysis results regarding the quality variable of subject teachers indicate that the significance of deviation from linearity is greater than 0.05, or $0.888 > 0.05$, So it can be stated that the relationship between the subject teachers' deliberation (X1) and the quality of history teachers (Y) is linear. Furthermore, the results of the linearity test show that the calculated F value is 0.944 and the table F value is 3.354 ($F_h < F_t$), indicating a linear relationship between the quality of subject teachers and the quality of history teachers. Meanwhile, the results of the analysis of the professional competency variable show that the significance of deviation

from linearity is > 0.05 , namely $0.612 > 0.05$; it can thus be stated that the relationship between professional competence (X2) and the quality of history teachers (Y) is linear, and the result of the linearity test in the F test table shows a calculated value of 1.397, and the F table value is 3.354 ($F_h < F_t$); thus indicating a linear relationship between professional competence and the quality of history teachers.

Based on the hypothesis testing of the research on correlational tests with a significance value (2-tailed) between the subject teachers' deliberation and professional competence towards the quality of history teachers being less than 0.05 ($0.001 < 0.05$), then there is a correlation among the tested variables. Meanwhile, the calculated r value between the subject teachers' deliberation and the quality of history teachers is 0.566, and the table r value (30:0.05) is 0.361. Because the calculated r is greater than the table r ($0.566 > 0.361$), it can be concluded that there is a positive relationship between the subject teachers' deliberation and the quality of history teachers. Similarly, the correlation between professional competence and the quality of history teachers is 0.563, while the table value (30:0.05) is 0.361. Because $r_{\text{count}} > r_{\text{table}}$ ($0.563 > 0.361$), it can be concluded that there is a positive relationship between professional competence and the quality of history teachers.

Based on the hypothesis testing of the research on the coefficient of determination test, according to Ghazali (2016), aims to measure the extent to which independent variables explain the variation in the dependent variable. The criteria for the coefficient of determination is between zero and one, or an interval from 0 to 1. A small R^2 (R square) value means that the ability of the independent variables to explain the variation in the dependent variable is minimal. The determination test can be assessed through R square, which is considered good if it is above 0.05. (Nurmilasari, 2019). From the results processed using SPSS Version 25 for Windows, the variable X1 has an R square value of 0.321 or 32.1%, which indicates that the variable of teacher subject deliberation (X1) has a significant relationship (influence) on the quality of history teachers amounting to 32.1%. Then, for the variable (X2), the R square value obtained is 0.414 or 41.4%, which indicates that the professional competence variable (X2) has a significant relationship (influence) on the quality of history teachers amounting to 41.4%.

From the description, it can be stated that there is a positive relationship between subject teachers' deliberation and professional competence towards the quality of history teachers. Based on the coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.321, it means that 32.1% of the changes in the quality of history teachers can be explained by the variable of subject teacher deliberation, with 41.4% of the contribution coming from the professional competence variable, while the remaining 26.5% is related to other variables not included in this research model.

This finding also reveals that there are still many other factors related to the quality of history teachers. This indicates that the improvement in the quality of

history teachers at the State High School in Banda Aceh will be less than optimal if it is only influenced by subject-teacher meetings and professional competence. So there are still many other variables that need to be studied to improve the quality of history teachers in Banda Aceh City State High Schools. Another factor, as stated by Nilsen & Gustafsson (2016), is that teacher quality can be improved in terms of teacher education, teaching readiness, self-confidence, work experience, and professional development. Improving teacher quality will support a supportive learning climate, clear teaching instructions and good classroom management.

CONCLUSION

Based on the previous descriptions and the results of data analysis and discussion of the results of the research carried out, it can be concluded as follows: The novelty is obtained from the magnitude of the research findings of each variable that are correlated with each other. The activity level of teachers in participating in subject-teacher meetings and professional competencies regarding the quality of history teachers at State Senior High School in Banda Aceh City is categorized as "sufficient." There is a significant relationship between subject-teacher meetings and the quality of history teachers at State Senior High School in Banda Aceh City. This means that the lack of subject-teacher meetings attended by teachers results in a deficiency in teachers' professional competence; conversely, sufficient professional competence in teachers is directly caused by participating in subject-teacher meetings, which are also lacking. However, this may be influenced by other variables that have a direct impact on the quality of history teachers.

POLICY SUGGESTIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

It is hoped that the Head of the Aceh Provincial Education Service as the person responsible for the quality of education in Banda Aceh City can make several efforts, especially to improve the quality of history teachers in State High Schools, including: Create a plan for activities that are programmed on an ongoing basis in the form of provision and training, focus group discussions, workshops (seminars), supervision programs, according to standards and development of school accreditation scores as well as other activities that can be carried out in an actual and efficient manner. Periodic and effective evaluation,

Provide sanctions for teachers, especially history subject teachers, who do not want to collaborate in developing their knowledge and are apathetic in subject teacher deliberation activities. Apart from that, making the subject teacher deliberation program a priority for developing history teachers in order to

improve work programs which can have an impact on improving the quality of history teachers.

For Teachers include: Utilize the various provisions received in order to increase the repertoire of knowledge, affection and skills carried out. Involving yourself in various activities and training that can build professionalism and good relationships between colleagues and with leaders, then help create a pleasant atmosphere, participate in meetings and have the courage to express good and positive opinions in school activities in particular. Teachers should play an active role in maintaining stable conditions or a good organizational atmosphere, trying to build healthy competition in work teams, establishing good communication with colleagues by providing assistance to teachers who experience difficulties in completing work.

LIMITATIONS

The results of this research only present the results of discussions in high schools in the local area, which include only three variables so that support for strengthening the results in improving history teachers can most likely still be contributed by other variables.

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